

Acute aldicarb (Chumbinho) poisoning in a young Brazilian woman: A case report

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Abstract

Chumbinho, the colloquial name for aldicarb, is a highly toxic carbamate insecticide illicitly sold in Brazil. Carbamates are potent inhibitors of the enzyme acetylcholinesterase, leading to a characteristic cholinergic toxidrome (muscarinic syndrome, nicotinic syndrome, and central nervous system acetylcholine accumulation). This case report describes a young Brazilian woman who presented to the emergency department in a coma with symptoms suggestive of cholinergic syndrome. Toxicological analysis revealed aldicarb metabolites. The patient was treated with atropine, resulting in the resolution of acute intoxication. Despite the WHO's 1991 ban on carbamates, systematic reviews indicate that acute intoxications and associated mortality rates remain high. Effective dissemination of information and education strategies are essential to prevent the use of these unauthorized products. Emergency physicians must develop expertise in toxicology to promptly recognize and treat these intoxications.

Take-home message: Chumbinho is a pesticidal insecticide containing aldicarb, a carbamate that inhibits cholinesterase activity. By inhibiting acetylcholinesterase, carbamates produce a typical cholinergic toxidrome. It is crucial to recognize the clinical aspects of this intoxication to promptly treat the poisoned patient with the antidote (atropine).

Keywords: aldicarb; atropine; cholinergic toxidrome; chumbinho; poisoning.

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INTRODUCTION

Chumbinho is the popular name for aldicarb, a highly toxic carbamate insecticide, illicitly sold in certain regions of Brazil [1]. Carbamates are potent inhibitors of the enzyme acetylcholinesterase, leading to a characteristic cholinergic toxidrome [2]. We report the case of a young Brazilian woman who presented to the emergency department in a coma with symptoms suggestive of cholinergic syndrome.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 32-year-old Brazilian woman was found unconscious on a subway mezzanine. No medical history was available upon arrival at the emergency department.

Vital signs upon arrival: blood pressure 90/60 mmHg; heart rate 100 beats/min; SatO₂ 97%; temperature 37°C. The patient was in a coma, non-responsive to verbal stimuli, reacting to painful stimuli with limb flexion and weak defense. Corneal reflex present, miotic pupils. No apparent focal motor deficits. Skin sweaty and pale, presence of sialorrhea. During the examination, clonus appeared in the right lower limb.

Arterial blood gas analysis: pH 7.30; pO₂ 99.9 mmHg; pCO₂ 32.0 mmHg; SatO₂ 97.8%; HCO₃ 16.2 mEq/L; BE -8. Blood tests showed: Hb 14.2 g/dL; RBC 4,740,000/mm³; Ht 42.8%; MCV 89 fl; WBC 14,200/mm³; Plt 346,000/mm³; glucose 200 mg/dL; Na 145 mEq/L; K 3.0 mEq/L; Ca 10.86 mg/dL; urea 26 mg/dL; creatinine 0.78 mg/dL; blood alcohol 87 mg/dL; pseudocholinesterase 0.65 kUI/L (normal range 4.5-14.5). A brain CT scan was normal. Therefore, it was a coma of undetermined nature. Excluding cerebral organic causes with CT, laboratory data showed metabolic acidosis with pseudocholinesterase consumption. Subsequently, the patient's sister arrived, reporting a history of anorexia and depressive syndrome. Acute voluntary intoxication with a probable anticholinesterase substance was suspected.

A serum sample was sent to the Institute of Forensic Medicine, confirming the presence of aldicarb metabolites. Meanwhile, some friends of the patient found a container of chumbinho (insecticide sold in Brazil) at her home. The patient was treated with atropine, resolving the acute intoxication.

DISCUSSION

Chumbinho is an insecticidal pesticide clandestinely sold in Brazil, responsible for numerous intoxications and deaths in this country [3-5]. This substance contains aldicarb, a carbamate whose mechanism of action is cholinesterase inhibition.

Carbamate pesticides were extensively used in the past; in 1990, a World Health Organization Task Force estimated that annual pesticide poisonings (including aldicarb) consisted of about 2 million intentional and 1 million unintentional cases [6]. Aldicarb was classified as “extremely hazardous” by the WHO [7], the highest toxicity category, leading the European Union to ban its use in 1991. Globally, 125 countries have currently banned aldicarb, according to the 2021 consolidated international list of banned pesticides by the Pesticide Action Network [8].

Carbamates inhibit acetylcholinesterase reversibly, producing a typical cholinergic toxidrome [2]. Acetylcholinesterase inhibition leads to acetylcholine accumulation, causing multiple symptoms: 1) Muscarinic syndrome: from parasympathetic stimulation; 2) Nicotinic syndrome: from stimulation of autonomic ganglia and motor nerve endings; 3) Central nervous system acetylcholine accumulation effects.

Muscarinic symptoms include bronchospasm, increased bronchial secretion, and dyspnea; miosis, lacrimation, visual disturbances; sialorrhea, sweating; urinary and fecal incontinence; bradycardia, and hypotension.

Nicotinic symptoms include weakness, ataxia, muscle fasciculations, paralysis; tachycardia, hypertension, hyperglycemia, and skin pallor (due to sympathetic ganglia stimulation).

Central nervous system symptoms include agitation, anxiety, confusion, delirium, hallucinations, dizziness, speech difficulties, loss of reflexes, central respiratory paralysis, seizures, and coma.

Given the reversible nature of the carbamates' bond with acetylcholinesterase, acute intoxication symptoms appear rapidly, predominantly muscarinic [9]. It is also essential to remember that tachycardia can occur due to adrenergic symptoms from nicotinic receptor activation in sympathetic ganglia [2], resulting in common mixed autonomic presentations.

Treatment involves decontamination (gastric lavage within 2 hours of ingestion, or activated charcoal and cathartics) and antidotal therapy with atropine. Atropine treatment is indicated upon symptom onset and suspected carbamate intoxication (even if tachycardia is present), with serial monitoring of pseudocholinesterase levels [2,10].

Previous reports indicated that pralidoxime use in carbamate intoxication was contraindicated [11-13]; recent experimental observations suggest that protection against carbamate toxicity is mainly due to atropine, not pralidoxime (which

shows neither beneficial nor harmful effects) [14]. Pralidoxime use is only indicated if there are predominant nicotinic signs (such as fasciculations) [15].

CONCLUSION

Despite the bans on its use, systematic reviews show that acute intoxications from these pesticides and their mortality rates remain high [10,16-19]. Dissemination of knowledge and information strategies are essential to prevent the use of these unauthorized products.

Emergency physicians must also develop expertise in toxicology to maintain a high suspicion based on the presence of cholinergic symptoms (cholinergic toxidrome), as waiting for laboratory results, which often take several hours, necessitates the rapid implementation of potentially lifesaving therapies.

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